

Scientific Cruise Report

1. Cruise participants

Clare Bradshaw: PI / Scientific cruise leader, DEEP/Stockholm University. Pre-planning, day-to-day planning during the cruise, onboard sampling and post-processing of samples.

Mattias Sköld: collaborator in the research project, SLU-Aqua. Onboard sampling and post-processing of samples

Aiden Florio: Masters student, DEEP/Stockholm University. Onboard sampling and post-processing of samples

2. Aim of the cruise

Evaluating the recovery trajectory of benthic community structure and function after cessation of bottom trawling

3. Cruise summary

Brief description of the daily activities: 45-60min transit from Simrishamn to the sampling station. Usually grab samples first, then cores. Grabs sieved immediately to extract macrofauna, cores sliced at 1cm intervals. Some saved in Ziplock bags and frozen onboard, some sieved to extract macrofauna. We usually managed 2 stations per day.

Problems that have been encountered: difficult to core some sites due to coarseness of sediment (but this was no fault of the research vessel).

Work area: A-L are the sampling stations:

4. **Scientific objectives**

Bottom trawling has complex interlinked physical, ecological and biogeochemical effects. It suspends sediment, alters seabed complexity, disrupts sediment structure and biogeochemistry. Benthic macrofauna communities are affected, the traits of different species determining their sensitivity to, and their potential to recover from, this disturbance.

There have been few large-scale investigations of recovery from long-term chronic trawling disturbance, due to the lack of areas in which to perform such studies. We have the unique possibility to study recovery of southern Baltic Sea seabeds after cessation of bottom trawling in 2019. We repeated our surveys from 2019/20/23 in order to follow the changes in physical sediment properties (porosity, grain size), benthic macrofauna communities (species composition, traits and depth distributions) and ecosystem function (based on species trait analysis and estimates of sediment carbon storage). Our study sites differ in previous trawling intensity, sediment and habitat type enabling us to evaluate differences in recovery in different settings.

5. **Station/activities log**

See attachment "Sampling Log and data document sheet.xlsx"

6. **Data document sheet**

See attachment "Sampling Log and data document sheet.xlsx"

7. **Preliminary results**

We are still working on the samples and data. The Masters student (Aiden Florio) has identified all the macrofauna species in the core samples and is now analysing the data together with similar data from 2019, 2020 and 2023 to see if there are any temporal changes and, if so, what factors drive these. His thesis will be finished early 2025 and a publication is also expected based on those data. In addition, we will perform a similar temporal analysis of the sediment characteristics. However, not all sediment samples are analysed yet. These analyses will be done during 2026 and will result in a paper.